

GLOBAL ECONOMIC PROSPECTS IN 2023

The impact of the global recession on the world's purchasing power.

Following the 1997 Asian Financial Crisis and the 2007-2008 Subprime Mortgage Crisis, the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) predicted that the world would face another severe financial crisis. In the World Bank report 'Global Economic Prospects' published in July 2022, the financial crisis was driven by several factors: the ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine, the Zero-Covid Policy in China, and a slow-moving

recovering economy.

A prominent consequence of the recession is the spike in the food supply chain, causing prices for goods and services around the world to rise. The situation also worsened as Russia and Ukraine, which are the world's top producers of wheat, are still embroiled in a war, causing world wheat prices to rise, as well as the prices of other food items.

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for almost all central banks around the world to follow after raising the base point rate by 75 basis points twice last year. An increase in the base rate raises a country's interest rate. The increase in interest rates will be followed by an increase in the price of goods and services. If this continues, it is feared that this will cause the world to suffer an economic recession.

Although Jerom Powell, chairman of the US Federal Reserve has issued a statement to dismiss the claim that the United States will not be plunged into an economic recession as a result of raising base points as one of the measures to curb inflation. In an era full of uncertainty, anything can happen. If this projection becomes a reality, then middle- and low-income earners, such as urban poor communities, are among the groups affected by this situation, as on average they have an income below RM2,000 while not being able to save for emergencies and the high cost of living in urban areas.

At the same time, the layoffs in tech companies such as Meta, Twitter, Google, Microsoft, Amazon, JPMorgan Chase, and others in the United States since the beginning of the year show that the technology industry is also not immune to the after-effects of the Covid-19 pandemic. Tech giants have also frozen hiring in 2023. In addition, the incident has also spread to Southeast Asia, where US\$1 billion of 'unicorn' companies or private companies such as Seagate Technology, Carsome, Shopee, iPrice, Stashaway, and others also took steps by reducing the number of employees. The massive layoffs are one of the measures taken in the face of the uncertain economic situation, and the companies will continue to focus

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on its profitability.

If an economic recession occurs, the purchasing power of consumers will decrease. Coupled with cases of mass layoffs, consumers' prospects for continuing their lives as it once were are increasingly bleak. Consumers would still have money to spend, but the amount of goods that can be purchased with the currency's value is decreasing in comparison to ten years ago. This indicates that the consumers' purchasing power has been drastically reduced daily. In addition, the imbalance between the rising costs of living while salary income remains the same without any change is causing

many people to be squeezed.

Even now, we are still puzzled as to whether 2023 will be the year of economic downturn in the US, which will undoubtedly spread around the world and affect all walks of life. It is still not too late for us to prepare for this financial crisis.

As the saying goes, "Thatch your roof before the rain begins," which is a fitting reminder for all of us. ⁵¹

Disclaimer: This article does not reflect the stance and policies of the institutions involved. It is the author's opinion, research, and experience while engaged in fieldwork.

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